

APHORISTIC SAYINGS IN LITERARY TEXTS

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Abstract. *This article examines aphoristic expressions in literary texts and their linguistic and cultural features. The study analyzes the role of aphorisms in artistic and journalistic works, their connection with the author’s context, and their transformation into quotations, winged expressions, and proverbs. The research highlights the stylistic and communicative significance of aphorisms in conveying universal ideas and cultural meanings.*

Keywords: *aphorism, literary text, linguoculturology, quotation, proverb*

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются афористические изречения в литературных текстах и их лингвокультурологические особенности. Анализируется роль афоризмов в художественных и публицистических произведениях, их связь с авторским контекстом, а также процесс превращения в цитаты, крылатые выражения и пословицы. Подчеркивается стилистическая и коммуникативная значимость афоризмов в передаче универсальных идей и культурных смыслов.*

Ключевые слова: *афоризм, литературный текст, лингвокультурология, цитата*

Annotatsiya. *Maqolada badiiy matnlardagi aforistik iboralar va ularning lingvokulturologik xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Aforizmlarning badiiy hamda publitsistik asarlardagi o‘rni, muallif konteksti bilan bog‘liqligi va iqtibos, qanotli so‘z hamda maqollarga aylanish jarayoni yoritiladi. Aforizmlarning universal g‘oyalalar va madaniy ma‘nolarni ifodalashdagi uslubiy hamda kommunikativ ahamiyati ko‘rsatib beriladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *aforizm, badiiy matn, lingvokulturologiya, iqtibos, maqol*

Introduction

Aphorisms are widely used in dramatic, literary, journalistic works, epistolary texts, memoirs, songs, and other genre varieties of verbal creativity. Aphoristic sayings included in literary texts differ fundamentally from aphorisms as an independent literary genre because, being an organic part of the entire work, they are closely connected with its content and may be misunderstood or even lose their meaning outside the author’s contexts. This served as a basis for scholars of aphoristics (for example, M.N. Epstein) to claim that not all generalized statements, especially those placed by the author into the mouths of literary characters, can be classified as aphorisms. Such judgments, firstly, do not possess a “universal meaning,” and secondly, “do not coincide with the writer’s integral worldview.”

While the second argument may partly be accepted (although this is not sufficient reason to refuse the study of aphoristic sayings of literary characters), the first argument does not correspond to linguistic reality. From a linguistic point of view, whether a saying possesses a “universal meaning,” that is, a generalized reflection of reality, does not directly depend on who its author is — the writer or the literary character created by the writer.

Main Body

Aphoristic sayings used in literary texts are in no way inferior to literary aphorisms as a genre, neither in content nor in the form of expression. They possess no less functional significance in speech and are no less popular among language speakers.

The expression of generalized thought is a universal feature of individual style (idiostyle) and has been known in European literature since antiquity. Thus, the famous poem “Works and Days” (“Ἔργα καὶ Ἡμέραι”, 8th–7th centuries BCE) by Hesiod consists almost entirely of teachings voiced by the author, as well as lists of advice and warnings, mainly in the form of aphorisms (“eternal truths”). The poet uses these aphorisms primarily as a means of persuasion, emphasizing that labor and its material benefit constitute the true meaning of human life.

A great number of aphoristic sayings on various subjects can also be found in the works of Pindar (ca. 518–442 or 438 BCE), one of the oldest poets and “the most Greek of all Greek poets.” For example, his “Pythian Odes” contain at least fifteen aphorisms structured syntactically as nominal sentences. Among them are the following (translated into Russian by M.L. Gasparov):

- “For a sailor, the first joy is a favorable wind from the harbor.”
- “A father’s glory is not strange to his son.”
- “Good success is the first reward; good fame is the second portion.”
- “The best destiny is wealth and the happiness of skill.”

Conclusion

Compilations of sayings extracted from literary works gained their greatest popularity only in the last century, when fundamental collections and encyclopedias appeared, often together with selected aphorisms from books belonging to the literary genre of aphorisms. These publications were created both within the framework of national literatures and on an international scale, covering either particular historical periods or all times and nations. Many aphorisms contained in literary works became widely known and function in speech as quotations from literary texts. Those that came into widespread use entered the category of winged expressions, while those that lost their associative connection with their original source in the minds of speakers became part of proverbs.

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